

Digital Death: Tradition and Technology in Design for Human Experience

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Abstract

The recent appearance of digital technology products in the realm of death is remarkable. While the necessary disposition of the body will always require some form of physical artifact, products associated with rituals of death are not governed by practicality alone. Objects used in rituals play a key role in the celebration of life, commemoration and mourning of the dead, and in cathartic experience for the bereaved. Recent innovation has been inspired by new demand for personalization and participation in the creation of meaningful rituals, and the artifacts that support them. Digital technology products including memorial web sites and DVDs provide flexibility in customization, personal contribution and creation of content, and access without the limitations imposed by physical space or location. However, the physical quality of human emotional experience continues to be important, facilitated through ceremonial action and the tangible sense of place associated with the dead. The integration of digital and physical product attributes in the realm of death has made only limited progress, embedding technology in otherwise traditional objects such as tombstones. New product opportunities exist for design to address the coexistence of the digital and physical, in the context of human experience.

Keywords: Death, design, digital, technology, experience, emotion

Introduction

With the inevitable fact of death comes the necessity of products. The body must be disposed of, thus creating the need for objects such as vessels for the transport and discrete burial or cremation of the dead. In Western funerary traditions this typically means a coffin or casket, and urns to house human ash remains following cremation. Memorial traditions are further connected with physical artifacts, including headstones or other tangible markers associated with the site of human burial or entombment. However, the objects associated with funeral and cemetery practices are not dictated by physical practicality alone. The artifacts selected and used in rituals play a critical role in orchestrating the celebration of life and mourning of the dead, and in the grieving process and cathartic experience of the bereaved (Hanington, 2004). While traditionally these products have been physical, recent innovation has witnessed the introduction of digital technology, both in virtual space, and as an integrated component of three-dimensional objects in the realm of death.

Of course, it must be recognized that artifacts connected with any ritual vary greatly by geographic location and cultural context. And while it may be argued that the Internet provides more universal access to web-based goods and services, this assumption would fail to acknowledge the vast number of people in the world without computer technology. Furthermore, cultural factors will remain primary determinants of personal and social choice, regardless of what products or services are made readily available. The history associated with various cultures is similarly varied. To manage the potential scope of the topic, this paper will therefore limit the discussion of ritual goods and practices to recent history in a Western context, primarily in the United States and Canada.

Death, Then and Now

Objects of death and mourning have a rich historical tradition. The practical necessity of caskets and urns aside, historic objects such as mourning wear and jewelry provided a coded ethic of attire both to identify the person suffering a loss, and for that person, a means of expressing tribute and bereavement (Figure 1). Dark, non-reflective clothing, and rings, brooches and pendants, often incorporating hair of the deceased, were considered intimate mementos honoring the dead. Additionally, everyday objects with graphic references to death

served as *memento mori*, stark reminders that everyone must die, and that a life lived righteously will prepare one for the hereafter.

Figure 1, Mourning wear (Lounsberry, 1994)

Modern artifacts have largely relied on surface treatments to fulfill the needs of the bereaved to pay tribute, and mourn the loss of a loved one. For example, a coffin may be adorned with hardware motifs of relevance to the dead, such as religious iconography or symbols associated with a person's life's work. Likewise, memorials may include graphic imagery and text, etched or supplied as statuary on grave markers. While certainly facilitating some degree of personalization, the range of goods available are limited in range and variation, particularly when compared to those of the past. Furthermore, the grieving process itself has been expedited, such that artifacts extending the rituals of mourning have all but disappeared. A return to work and the routines of normal life following the loss of a loved one is expected in short order, certainly condensed from periods of mourning often lasting several years during the early part of the 20th century.

Despite the evident differences between past and present, a similar human purpose is served through the rituals of mourning. "In order to ease the psychological burden of bereavement mourning allowed, then as now, the individual time in which to spread the potentially damaging effects of the loss, the sudden, awful absence." (Llewellyn, 1991: 85).

Furthermore, a theory of "two bodies" is as pertinent to a discussion of memorial artifacts today as in past. The memorial attempts to preserve the social body by commemorating the dead to individuals and in the collective memory, despite the loss of the physical body (Llewellyn, 1991). An examination of modern products and practices, in contrast to the past, reveals several changes in means, but to similar ends, in practical matters, and in facilitating emotional aspects of tribute, bereavement and mourning.

Death and Innovation

Recent innovation has altered the landscape of funeral and memorial products, many with significant points of historical reference. For example, a resurgence of mourning jewelry now includes services for turning the ashes of cremated loved ones into artificial diamonds and colored gemstones (Salter, 2005). Similarly, pendants and other items of “cremation jewelry” are designed to house the cremated ash or hair of the dead, or dried flowers (Figure 2, www.perfectmemorials.com). Other extreme options for the disposal of human remains include placing ash in small vials that are then launched into outer space on rockets (www.memorialspaceflights.com). In contrast to these high-technology trends, environmental advocates promote the burial of bodies in biodegradable vessels or shrouds, in eco friendly memorial grounds, with stones from the surrounding landscape or trees planted in place of granite headstones (Sherman, 2003). The limited array of products and services traditionally made available is clearly being challenged, with increased demand for a selection of unique and personal goods.

Figure 2, Modern cremation jewelry (www.perfectmemorials.com)

As important as the innovation is the source of inspiration for these new products and services, corresponding to increased demand for personalization and participation in rituals. No longer are people willing to relegate all responsibility for designing ceremonies, and selecting the supporting artifacts, to professionals who typically have had no connection to the deceased prior to their passing. The bereaved are choosing to be involved, participating in the creation of meaningful rituals through the planning and nature of ceremonial activity. “Grievors are turning away from funeral homes in droves, opting instead for personalized home memorials. The new do-it-yourself mentality has given root to a growing industry that

is replacing the act of choosing a tombstone with more flexible, less sanitized mourning practices.” (Sherman, 2003).

Digital Death and Design

The introduction of digital artifacts in the realm of death is equally remarkable, and similarly influenced by trends of personalization and participation. In addition, the previously absent discussion of death in design terms is suddenly changing, and connections to human experience are now being made in the most unlikely of places. “Funeral directors, morticians, and cemeteries are discovering the customer-experience thing, adopting technology to personalize and speed a trade long rooted in cookie-cutter sameness.” (Salter, 2005). Corresponding to a central hallmark of human centered design, the invitation for users to participate in the creation of experiences through a “scaffold” provided by design is now, finally, entering the realm of death.

Internet cemeteries have been established for some time now, with evident benefits over the traditional memorial park. For example, the World Wide Cemetery (www.cemetery.org) and Virtual-Memorials.com enable users to create personal memorials with text, visuals, and music (Figure 3). In addition to providing a forum for offering words or images, Internet-based memorial sites accommodate access to posted information by friends and family across disparate locations. The limitations imposed by physical real estate are removed with virtually unlimited space for commemorative content, and the environmental impact of excessive land use demanded by traditional memorial markers is reduced. Furthermore, digital memorials eliminate the concern for material deterioration over time, at least insofar as we can assume enduring technology.

Figure 3, Virtual-Memorials.com

Similarly, web logs and forums provide an immediate outlet for personal expressions of tribute, grief and solace, again without the limitations imposed by geographic location or the use of physical space. Individuals with even basic skills and technology may craft personal web sites designed for others to add and view messages of tribute and condolence. One web designer said that he found an outlet for dealing with his own grief and the offer of support through the creation of a web site for a family close to him suffering a tragic loss.

Increasingly, funeral homes or local newspapers provide services for contributing online messages of tribute and sympathy (Levin, 2006). In very public tragedies, friends, family, and strangers alike utilize these sites, finding some comfort in a venue where they can offer words of empathic support or condolences.

The instantaneous nature of web-based memorials may in some ways be compared to so-called “spontaneous memorials”, the physical displays of objects, flowers, and messages that suddenly arise at a site of death, particularly in the case of accidental deaths. Presumably, whether through digital or physical means, some comfort is taken in a channel provided for the outpouring of shared grief. “Spontaneous memorials are populist phenomena, ways for people to mark their own history. They create a public place for communities united in grief and sometimes anger.” (Senie, 1999: 25). Both physical and digital manifestations of spontaneous memorials serve to confirm the importance of preserving the social body.

Web-cast ceremonies facilitate virtual attendance at funerals by those who cannot be there in person. The live broadcast may address the needs of families dispersed across geographic location, and those with travel limitations imposed by disability, finances, or competing life

events. Memorial DVDs provide portable media that can be easily reproduced and distributed as keepsakes for multiple friends and family members. Composed of photographic montages to tell of a life history, DVDs or memorial videos are increasingly offered by even the most traditional of funeral homes. Multimedia presentations are now a common feature of many funeral services, and are explicitly promoted as the specialty of some (for example, see www.hollywoodforever.com).

Death and Experience

The cathartic experience of mourning corresponds to the defining characteristics of emotional experience. Emotional experience, differentiated from transitory reactions to products or environments, is comprised of sustained, reflective responses, or mood (DiSalvo, Forlizzi, and Hanington, 2002). The qualities that commonly constitute a positive emotional experience surrounding death are a level of engaged participation to overcome elements of felt helplessness, the satisfaction taken in creating a meaningful ritual suitably paying tribute to the life of a loved one, and some degree of memorializing, serving both as an enduring record of the deceased, and providing a tangible sense of place for visitation, given the absence of the physical body. Collectively, these elements form a basis for mourning, and cathartic experience reducing the effects of painful loss.

The flexibility afforded by digital technology aligns well with the qualities of emotional experience. While some may remain in the hands of professionals, many products offer opportunity for direct involvement by individuals, either in their creation, or in the contribution of content. Memorial DVDs and web sites are easily created with accessible technology and basic skills. Yet even without the skills or motivation to design and build these digital artifacts, people can contribute easily to the content of memorial videos or web sites. The mere process of selecting appropriate photographs and text, and the ease of adding messages of sympathy or tribute, provide a needed outlet for participation and personal expression. In the words of gerontology professor Kenneth Doka, “Whatever our technology is, whatever our mode of communication is, we have always used it for some form of memorializing. Those kinds of messages really help people in their grief, in that it gives them the sense that the life was meaningful.” (Levin, 2006).

Despite the qualities of human emotional experience facilitated by technology, practices deeply rooted in the physical remain. In many cultures these practices are directly connected to the body, such as family involvement in the washing and preparation of the dead. Even in cultures where bodily preparations are the role of the professional, other physical activities still play a critical role in mourning rituals. For example, the physical offerings left as spontaneous memorials are “evidence of the existence of collected as well as collective memory, reflecting various personal strategies for mourning.” (Senie, 2003). The physical experience of visiting and maintaining gravesites can provide a sense of place associated with the dead, necessary for some as an aspect of mourning. Many people visit a memorial on significant anniversaries, and take some solace in physical activity such as cleaning the stone or placing flowers and objects of tribute on the grave. Technology has only been able to approximate this through options for contributing digital messages, or leaving “virtual” flowers on the “grave” (www.cemetery.org).

Recent innovation points to limited examples of an integrated approach that attempts to reconcile the need for physical experience with the benefits of technology. The Serenity Vidstone is a 6 by 8 inch monitor housed in a traditional gravestone, capable of playing a 10-minute video loop (Figure 4, www.vidstone.com). A plastic cover protects it from inclement weather. However, while the Vidstone integrates the functional aspects of a grave marker and digital technology, it does not necessarily present an integrated solution by aesthetic or experiential criteria. The mere insertion of a video screen into otherwise traditional memorial design fails to challenge existing form and materials, presenting an uneasy marriage of old and new.

Figure 4, Serenity Vidstone (www.vidstone.com)

The Memory Medallion represents a slightly better union of tradition and technology, with a battery-sized disk embedded in the tombstone, activated by a “touch-wand” that then transmits messages to a user’s laptop or other handheld computer device (Salter, 2005; www.memorymedallion.com). Although this invention similarly embeds technology in an otherwise traditional artifact, it leaves the grave marker intact for what it is, and relies on appropriate existing technological devices to handle digital elements. In the Vidstone and the medallion, the opportunity for new product innovation that suitably integrates the need for physical interaction with the flexibility afforded by new technology in the context of human emotional experience has not been fully realized. It is inevitable that further innovation in pervasive technology will inspire products where physical and digital interactions must co-exist. This is an area yet to be fully exploited by design, but one that has excellent potential.

Conclusion

The experience facilitated by digital products may be better described as one in parallel with the physical, rather than in place of it. The presence of the body will forever dictate some need for objects connected with the handling and disposition of the dead. Rising cremation rates have inspired innovation that deals with sanitary remains through creative means. Digital technology has served well to fulfill the need for “place” where no physical memorial exists, for instance when ashes are scattered. In the absence of a physical body and artifact, digital technology may indeed ensure that the social body is preserved. Furthermore, the

flexibility afforded by technology facilitates participation without the limitations imposed by personal location or distance. Accessible technology democratizes direct involvement by people no longer reliant solely on the specialized skills of professionals in the “death care” industries. The increase in participation enhances the opportunities for personalization in the creation of ritual ceremonies, and in the artifacts that support them.

We must continue to recognize that for many people, the physical will remain a vital component of death and mourning. Based upon personal, cultural, or religious beliefs, burial of the body and a tangible memorial may be crucial. Furthermore, it must be acknowledged that the qualitative difference of physical experience associated with tangible objects and place can still be contrasted to digital interactions. Only tentative steps have been taken to satisfy the shortcomings in this area. Opportunities abound for new interactions and visual language in product design. In the realm of death, true innovation will be made evident through the creation of products that recognize the physical, capitalize on the digital, and reconcile them both in the holistic context of human emotional experience.

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